

Article information

Article title

CORE-WESM: A multi-scale whole energy system model to support integrated energy planning in Kenya

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Related research article

None

Abstract

The evolving governance system of Kenya's energy sector is centered around county-level energy planning and its integration with the national level. This paper presents a county-disaggregated version of the open-source whole energy system model OSeMOSYS-Kenya in support of this integration process. The COunty-REsolved Whole Energy System Model (CORE-WESM) introduces two methodological elements,

- the spatial disaggregation of the model through a downscaling approach as a basis for further integration of county-specific data and plans as and when developed, and
- a multi-scale modelling workflow to allow for a flexible application of the model.

CORE-WESM can support integrated energy planning by facilitating scenario modelling analyses that provide insights and a tool for communication across governance levels. The model has been developed in collaboration with county and national stakeholders in Kenya.

Graphical abstract

Specifications table

Subject area	Energy
More specific subject area	Energy modelling
Name of your method	COunty-RESolved Whole Energy System Model (CORE-WESM)
Name and reference of original method	The CORE-WESM is a county-disaggregated version of the open-source OSeMOSYS-Kenya whole energy system model. Model: Lubello, P., Oduor, J., & Pye, S. (2025). OSeMOSYS Kenya Whole Energy System Model (v0.1.1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15056038 ; Documentation: Lubello, P., Akute, M., & Pye, S. (2023). OSeMOSYS Kenya WESM - Documentation (0.1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425600
Resource availability	The CORE-WESM code and data are available under a MIT and CC-BY-3.0 license, respectively, at: https://github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/CORE-WESM

Background and Motivation

Kenya is actively planning how to meet increasing energy demand in the coming decade and beyond, across all sectors of the economy. The Energy Act 2019 stipulates that this planning must be devolved to its 47 county governments, via county energy plans (CEPs), and integrated into national planning via the Integrated National Energy Planning (INEP) framework. This devolved approach poses challenges for the planning community, which has traditionally undertaken modelling at a national level with limited consideration of subnational areas. Analysis allowing for consideration of multi-scale governance is typically limited [1].

The county planning process is ongoing but has so far been limited by a lack of resources, data, and planning capacity. A recent review found that only six counties had so far completed their CEPs, with a further 15 plans in development [2]. Of those completed, different approaches to energy planning have been used, along with different modelling tools, e.g., OnSSET and LEAP. This has resulted in a fragmented planning landscape, making it challenging to integrate into the national INEP framework.

At the national level, a key planning tool developed to support whole system energy planning is OSeMOSYS [3,4], which has been used to model scenarios for Kenya's recent e-cooking strategy [5] and assess their green hydrogen strategy [6]. However, for wider use in the INEP process, the model is limited as it represents Kenya as a single region, and therefore none of the counties explicitly.

The proposed methodology is a national-scale model called CORE-WESM (COunty-REsolved Whole Energy System Model) which allows for the representation of multi-level governance, encompassing both national and county levels. Such a model structure can facilitate the incorporation of county-specific information, including from CEPs where they are completed or in progress, and enable their aggregation into a national perspective based on county planning. Furthermore, the impact of national policy on counties can also be considered. A key additional advantage from a planning perspective is that the framework enables information from CEPs to be incorporated, but default downscaled data can be used if CEPs are not yet available. In this way, the planning process can progress, and CEP data incorporated when available.

It is important to note that CORE-WESM is not intended as a replacement of county-specific CEPs, which are detailed plans to understand current and future energy needs, covering resource assessment, notably for bioenergy and renewables, energy access status and needs, energy efficiency improvement potential, bioenergy use, and electricity demand [7]. As noted earlier, the framework is focused on improving the representation of county energy systems and planning priorities at a national scale. To that end, a scoping exercise was undertaken with Kenyan stakeholders to determine the design of the modelling framework [7,8]. This considered model boundaries (sector scope and coverage), data (needs and availability), and design (functionality and workflow).

An accompanying study explored the development of energy demand projections for future use in CORE-WESM, based on the MAED modelling framework [9].

Method details

This section describes the workflow of creating and running the CORE-WESM model starting with an instance of the national OSeMOSYS-Kenya model. In describing the workflow, the section also highlights the structure and functionality of CORE-WESM. The model is based on the open-source energy modelling framework OSeMOSYS. OSeMOSYS is a bottom-up linear optimization framework to facilitate long-term energy planning. A general introduction to the OSeMOSYS modelling framework is provided by Howells et al. [10], while a description of the underlying national energy system model OSeMOSYS-Kenya can be found in its documentation [4].

The workflow consists of two core elements that also underpin the multi-scale functionality of CORE-WESM, with each of them broken down into a number of substeps. The workflow steps are:

1. Creating the CORE-WESM input data set
 - 1.1. Downscaling the national OSeMOSYS-Kenya model
 - 1.2. Integrating additional county-resolved datasets
 - 1.3. Integrating county-specific data or plans
2. Running the CORE-WESM model and analyzing results
 - 2.1. Configuring the workflow and model run
 - 2.2. Performing model runs
 - 2.3. Analyzing results

The steps are explained in detail in the following subsections. This focuses on a conceptual perspective on the workflow while more technical information is provided in the model documentation.

1. Creating the CORE-WESM input data set

The first step – as well as the entire workflow – revolves around a number of processing scripts implemented in the Python programming language. To be able to perform the workflow, a Python environment needs to be set up, e.g.,

using the package management system *conda*. An environment configuration file is provided in the model repository and sets up an environment for the entire workflow.

1.1. Downscaling the national OSeMOSYS-Kenya model

This section describes the downscaling approach to generate an initial CORE-WESM dataset that allows for the representation of multi-level governance by moving from a single node to a county-resolved model.

Building on the national OSeMOSYS-based Kenya WESM, the county-resolved WESM is obtained by disaggregating it into a county-resolved input dataset. The disaggregation approach considers the residential, agriculture, industry and transport sectors, both in terms of their base year characterizations and projections of demand and other parameters. The overall methodology for country-to-county disaggregation and downscaling of data is presented in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. COUNTRY-TO-COUNTY DISAGGREGATION AND DATA DOWNSCALING.

The disaggregation of the national model into a county-resolved dataset involves three basic steps. First (Box A), the starting point for the downscaling is the national model dataset containing all input data of the national model in terms of its parameters¹ and sets in the form of a spreadsheet file in .xlsx format.

Second (Box B), the dataset is then disaggregated into sector-specific files because each sector is downscaled using population or gross county product (GCP). The script `to_sector.py` processes the national-level parameter model stored in an Excel file (`WESM.xlsx`) and disaggregates its data into a sector-separated dataset. This conversion involves grouping technologies and commodities by their respective sectors and distributing relevant data into sector-specific files. For instance, some of the outputs are:

- **Sectoral Files:** One file per sector (e.g., `Agriculture.xlsx`, `Electricity.xlsx`) containing disaggregated data.
- **Set.xlsx:** Consolidates set-related data.
- **Emission.xlsx:** Contains emission-related data.
- **Other.xlsx:** Stores data that do not match specific sectoral mappings.

Once the sector-separated dataset is prepared, it can be downscaled to the county level (Box C) using the `to_counties.py` script. The script generates a county--resolved dataset by downsampling the residential sector based on population and other sectors according to gross county product (GCP) by economic activity. The Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS) provides both information on population by county and GCP by economic activity at the county level. The proportion of economic activities involving agriculture, industry, services, and transportation is

¹ Parameter definition: <https://osemosys.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

used to downscale data for the respective sectors, while the fraction of population in each county is used to downscale the residential sector. Table 1 provides an excerpt of the underlying GCP data and highlights the variations across counties in economic structure captured through the downscaling.

TABLE 1. GCP BY ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

COUNTY Name	COUNTY Id	Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	Mining and quarrying	Manufacturing	Electricity supply
Baringo	BA	29185	146	4523	132
Bomet	BO	84771	721	11275	420
Bungoma	BU	90500	348	8151	785
Meru	MU	182778 (1.85%)	3655	16334	1852
Nairobi	NI	4312 (0.04%)	877	298415	28256

NOTE. GCP IN KSH MILLION, DATA ADAPTED FROM [11].

For instance, comparing the agricultural contributions from two counties, Nairobi and Meru, to the total GCP in Kenya, highlights that Nairobi's contribution is significantly lower than Meru's. Figure 2 presents a visual representation of the downscaling approach using population and GCP. The resulting outputs include:

- **County Folders:** Contains sectoral data files adapted to each county's population and GCP.
- **National Folder:** Retains non-disaggregated data and ensures compatibility with other sectors.
- **Updated Set.xlsx File:** Contains data on commodities, fuel, and technology.
- **Multi-scale Folder:** Contains data defining the multi-scale structure of the model

FIGURE 2. COUNTRY-TO-COUNTY DISAGGREGATION AND DATA DOWNSCALING USING GCP FRACTIONS AND POPULATION FRACTIONS

1.2. Integrating additional county-resolved datasets

County-resolved datasets are those that provide data specifically at the county level. They therefore offer information specific to each county, which is crucial for CORE-WESM to capture local differences and variations. For example, these datasets can include county-specific demographics, appliance ownership, and lighting and cooking sources. Table 2 presents some exemplary datasets. This data could, for example, provide information on the number of households that own electrical appliances and the sources of lighting and cooking.

TABLE 2. COUNTY-RESOLVED DATASETS

County-resolved datasets	Reference
Kenya Integrated Household Budget Survey (2015-2016)	[12]

These datasets can be an important component for disaggregating a national energy model into county-level, ensuring that local energy needs and infrastructure are accurately reflected in the model. The country-resolved datasets – or aggregated datasets– can also be used to define different scenarios. For instance, the current disaggregation into county-level and further downscaling of data includes information on stove usage at the county level, which is sourced from the DHS. DHS provides data at both county level and across urban and rural areas. This data was used to estimate the share of stove usage types, which were then incorporated into the CORE-WESM for each county.

1.3. Integrating county-specific data or plans

County-specific data and plans are a crucial component for further development of a refined CORE-WESM. They include detailed, on-the-ground information directly sourced from individual county administrations, as featured in the County Energy Plans (CEPs). These CEPs follow a framework outlined in the Integrated National Energy Plan (INEP) document, that is flexible to the needs of different counties. Counties can choose their methodologies to develop scenarios, which may vary in respect of the outputs depending on the approach taken.

For example, the Makueni County Energy Plan can provide county-specific data that can enhance the CORE-WESM. It includes assessments of local energy resources such as biomass, solar, wind, and small-scale hydropower potential, which can be used to calibrate the supply-side modelling for the county [14]. On the demand side, the plan offers details into access to modern cooking solutions, barriers to clean cooking adoption, and potential intervention strategies, which also could contribute to a better calibration of the cooking sector in the model. This type of localized information is valuable for refining both demand and supply assumptions at the county level [15].

2. Running the CORE-WESM model and analysing results

Following the creation of a CORE-WESM input data set, the model can be run and results analysed for policy insights. The CORE-WESM run setup consists of three elements.

First, it requires the input data set with data for each scenario to be run as derived under the previous workflow step. The second element is an OSeMOSYS model file. The OSeMOSYS model file contains the actual structure of the linear programme, in terms of its sets, parameters, variables, constraints, and objective function [10]. The OSeMOSYS model file used for the CORE-WESM is written in GNU Mathprog and is provided in the model repository. Third, a workflow script and related modules are provided and need to be set up alongside configuration files to facilitate the workflow. More details on this are provided in the following subsections that outline the three steps using the workflow script to run the model. Figure 3 shows a graphical overview of the workflow.

FIGURE 3. SIMPLIFIED FLOW DIAGRAMME OF THE APPLICATION OF THE CORE-WESM WITH WORKFLOW STEPS HIGHLIGHTED.

2.1. Configuring the workflow and model run

The initial step involves the configuration of the workflow in general – if not done previously –, as well as the definition of the model run itself. The configuration of the workflow is based on two different configuration files written in the YAML format – a data and a workflow configuration file.

The data configuration file describes the structure of the input data set in terms of its parameters, sets, and their relevant specifications, e.g., default values. This configuration file follows the format of similar files used for the OSeMOSYS processing library otoole [16]. A version of the file is part of the model repository and only requires updates if the structure of the model dataset is altered, e.g., additional OSeMOSYS parameters are added. An exemplary excerpt of the data configuration file with the specification of the *CapacityFactor* parameter is shown in Box 1.

BOX 1: EXCERPT OF DATA CONFIGURATION FILE SHOWING THE SPECIFICATION OF THE CAPACITYFACTOR PARAMETER.

```
CapacityFactor:
  indices: [REGION,TECHNOLOGY,TIMESLICE,YEAR]
  type: param
  dtype: float
  default: 1
```

The workflow configuration file defines both general and run-specific workflow parameters. General workflow parameters include, for example, file paths to the model input data set and data configuration file, and the definition of scenarios based on scenario levers in the model input data set. Moreover, the file parameterizes the model runs to be performed, e.g., in terms of the scenarios to be run, the mathematical solver to be used, and the spatial configuration of the model runs. This will be explained in more detail in the following step. A default version of the configuration file with explanatory comments is provided in the model repository.

2.2. Performing model runs

The second step entails performing model runs by running the workflow Python script. The script makes use of an additional Python module² with a number of processing functions based on standard Python data manipulation packages like Pandas, as well as the multi-scale modelling framework frato³. The execution of the script is shaped by the configuration file described above, which defines what and how a number of core steps are performed. The following paragraphs highlight the core steps of the workflow – these can be performed completely using the script or be separated out and performed manually, e.g., to run the model optimization itself in a cloud-based environment. The workflow definition through the configuration file allows for the operation of the model without extensive use of Python – a potential barrier to use. Yet, if further variations or extensions are required the script and processing module can also form the basis of extended or completely new workflow setups for future analyses.

First, the script is loading and processing the input data set. After the data set files are read into Python data structures, several processing steps are conducted if triggered in the configuration file, e.g., the renaming of model sets. A key processing step is the temporal aggregation of the model. Given the disaggregation into a county-resolved model increases the spatial resolution and with it the computational complexity of the model, the workflow includes functionality for a user-defined aggregation of the intra-year timeslices and the years represented in the model. This optional disaggregation can be required to reduce the complexity of model runs and make the optimization of the model feasible within set computational limits.

² The module is currently provided as a single Python file alongside the CORE-WESM specific workflow files but might in future be published as a separate package.

³ More information about the frato framework can be found in its GitHub repository (<https://github.com/lhofbauer/frato>) and documentation (<https://fratoo.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>).

Following this, the multi-scale structure is initialized and the data for the model run generated. For this, the input data set is processed using the multi-scale modelling framework *fratoo*. *fratoo* is a compact, Python-based modelling framework wrapped around OSeMOSYS to facilitate the development and running of multi-scale models. The creation of a *fratoo* model based on the loaded and processed input data set enables the flexible generation of run data with varying spatial configurations based on the framework. For example, the model can be run for a single county, for Kenya as a whole with all counties being aggregated, or a full model run with all counties represented explicitly. More detail on this functionality is provided in the *fratoo* documentation. The run data are written out as an OSeMOSYS data file in GNU Mathprog syntax.

For the optimization of the model run, the script first uses the open-source linear programming package GLPK [17] to process the data file and OSeMOSYS model file into a linear programme (LP) file. The processing and optimization of the linear programme defined in the LP file is then done using existing LP solvers. The workflow currently includes an interface to the open-source cbc and HiGHS solver, but additional solvers can be added or the optimization of the LP file be run separately.

The results from the optimization of the model are processed and saved. The processing includes, for example, the calculation of additional variables not provided by the solver, as well as the addition of the input data set. The workflow script also includes basic plotting functionality for an initial assessment of the modelling results. The result dataset is saved as a set of CSV files each including the data for a parameter or variable.

2.3. Analysing results

The last step is the analysis of optimisation results based on the focus or research question of the study to be conducted. As indicated under step 2.2, the standard workflow script only includes basic plotting options that can form the basis for an initial analysis of the model results. For a more comprehensive analysis, the result data can be either be plotted or otherwise post-processed using any preferred software, e.g., using other Python scripts or spreadsheet software, or the workflow script itself can be enhanced. Illustrative results are presented in the following section.

Illustrative results

This section presents illustrative results for a reference scenario to highlight the purpose and application of the CORE-WESM. Scenario analyses can consider single county insights, e.g., in terms of the sectoral final energy consumption (Figure 4), integration and comparison across county pathways, e.g., in terms of final energy consumption of different fuels (Figure 5), as well as for integrated national insights, e.g., in terms of technology deployment for residential cooking (Figure 6).

FIGURE 4. FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN THE DISAGGREGATED SECTORS IN MERU (LEFT), NAIROBI (RIGHT). THE FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION FIRST DECREASES DUE TO A SHIFT TO MORE EFFICIENT TECHNOLOGIES, IN PARTICULAR IN THE RESIDENTIAL COOKING SECTOR, BEFORE INCREASING AGAIN DUE TO POPULATION GROWTH.

FIGURE 5. FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION ACROSS ALL COUNTIES

FIGURE 6. COOKING SECTOR, AGGREGATED ACROSS RURAL/URBAN AND ALL COUNTIES

Method validation

As with other energy models exploring future pathways, it is not possible to validate CORE-WESM against empirical data [18]. This highlights the importance of the open-source character of CORE-WESM – both in terms of its code and data – which ensures transparency in structure and assumptions and enables reproducibility. This does not only entail the model being published under an open license but also a clear structure and documentation that allows for a comprehensible model and workflow [19].

Limitations

As indicated before, the current version of the CORE-WESM is not a final product – to the extent any model can be – but the foundation for a model whose further development, in particular in terms of the inclusion of county-level datasets and county energy plans, is envisioned to be part of and shape the future integration of county and national energy planning in Kenya. Hence, the current version has limitations in terms of its readiness for detailed scenario analyses.

With regard to the application of the model, two major limitations can be highlighted. First, the functionality of the current workflow script, e.g., with regard to solver interfaces and plotting functionality, is limited. Second, and closely connected to the OSeMOSYS model file and input dataset being used, the optimization of a full model run is computationally expensive and requires a computing environment with large memory, even if temporally

aggregated. This can be reduced through, among others, a more memory-efficient OSeMOSYS model file or a restructuring of the input data set to, e.g., reduce the number of technologies and fuels.

Having outlined the process for disaggregating the national model into county-level modules and the potential for the integration of county-resolved and county-specific data in the previous sections, the following paragraphs discuss in more detail the limitations and data challenges that should be addressed to ensure robust analysis.

CORE-WESM can align with existing CEPs and local data by integrating such county-specific datasets. However, harmonizing this data comes with challenges due to data fragmentation, variations in quality, and differences in the modelling approaches used across counties, such as OsEMOSYS, LEAP, and OnSSET, linked to varying stages of CEP development.

To address these challenges, a data harmonization strategy can be implemented. Such a strategy could involve standardising variable names and formatting to seamlessly integrate various data sources into CORE-WESM. A centralised data repository for sharing and standardising energy data across counties can be established to support consistency and improve accessibility. For instance, the Kenyan Data Repository intends to serve as a centralised and collaborative platform for sharing data among stakeholders in Kenya [20].

Moreover, county-resolved datasets can be integrated, e.g., from the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS). Additionally, county level energy demand inputs can be calibrated using the results from Electricity Demand Mapping based on Open-Source data (EDeMOS) tool [21]. This method uses open-source data sets to estimate electricity consumption for residential and service sectors [9].

Engaging stakeholders at both the national and county levels is essential for effective data sourcing and ongoing enhancements. For example, it is crucial to source regular updates from national agencies such as Kenya Power and Lighting Company (KPLC), Energy and Petroleum Regulatory Authority (EPRA), and Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS). Moreover, strengthening partnerships with county stakeholders to support capacity building and promote collaborative data sharing is equally important. This approach will also enable model improvements by integrating supplementary datasets, including renewable resource potential, transportation, and waste management at the county level. Establishing such collaborations could ensure that CORE-WESM remains up-to-date and relevant for current planning processes.

Ethics statements

None.

CRediT author statement

Leonhard Hofbauer: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Ariane Millot:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation. **Roberto Heredia-Fonseca:** Methodology, Software, Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Neve Fields:** Data curation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Pietro Lubello:** Methodology, Data curation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Adam Hawkes:** Conceptualization, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Funding acquisition. **Steve Pye:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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